

A Study of Social Motives of Secondary School Teachers in West Bengal

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ABSTRACT

The teacher is the most important element of an education system. The teacher's personal characteristics, his/her proficiency as the manager of learning activities, skills in monitoring the learning process and in teaching, background and relations with students and other individuals influence his/her study and success within the classroom. Social motives are general characteristics of a person and since they are learned motives, their strength differs greatly from one individual to other. The purpose of the study was to compare the social motives of the secondary school teachers of West Bengal. The study was conducted upon 382 secondary school teachers. The major variable was social motive and the categorical variable was gender (male & female), locale (rural & urban) and training (trained & untrained). The Social Motive Scale (SMS), by Dr. Singh and Dr. Pandey (2010) were used in the study. The results showed that there exist significant differences between male school teachers and female school teachers in their social motives but no significant difference between rural and urban as well as trained and untrained school teachers of West Bengal.

Keywords: Social Motives, Secondary school teachers

INTRODUCTION

Social motives are otherwise known as acquired or learned motives. These are some complex forms of motives, which result mainly from man's interaction with his social environment. These motives are called social because they are learned in social groups. These peculiar human motives can be looked upon as general states that lead to particular behaviors. Social motives are general characteristics of a person and since they are learned motives, their strength differs greatly from one individual to other. It is unique to one and depends upon ways of perceiving things. The quality and performance of teachers are always considered as determining factors for the success of educational changes. Since the 1980s, the decline in quality of teachers has become an issue of concern to the education sector worldwide (Ballou & Podgursky, 1997). Scholars and educators have identified several major problems faced by recruitment and retention in the teaching profession, such as the teaching profession fails to attract bright young people (Murnane, 1991), a disproportionate share of higher ability teachers leave teaching to pursue for other careers (Ballou & Podgursky, 1997; Murnane, 1991) and the under-representation of both qualified minority teachers (Newby, Smith, Newby & Miller, 1995) and males in the primary school teaching force (Johnston, Mckeown & McEwen, 1999). It is obvious that the quality of teaching force is not governed only by the qualification,

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pedagogical knowledge and teaching skill of teachers, but also their attitude, enthusiasm, dedication and commitment in teaching. It is determined by the social motives of teachers to conduct the teaching and how they perceive teaching attitudes in the classrooms. At the same time, the teachers' behaviour and teaching performance may also be influenced by their conceptions about teaching and learning and their confidence to teach which the part of their motivation is.

Natrajan, S (1988) in her thesis work explored the need motivation of student learners. Her objectives were to study the relationship between the four need motivation: n-Achievement, n-Affiliation, n-Power and n-Approval and to study the nature of the above mentioned four levels of student learners on various backgrounds in the Chhattisgarh region. She found there was no significant territorial variation on either of the four need motivation as well as authoritarianism between the four levels of student learners. A significant difference between graduate and post-graduate students was observed on n-Ach.

Maria de Lourdes Mata's (2012) paper aims to understand how certain different but interrelated variables such as background, motivation and social support could lead to an explanation of teachers' attitudes towards teaching math and to an understanding of the defining characteristics of these attitudes in the school environment. The study utilizes an adaptation of the "Intrinsic Motivation Inventory" assessing main determinants of intrinsic motivation. The results revealed that, in general, teachers held positive attitudes towards teaching mathematics and also highlighted the main effects of grade and math teaching achievement on these attitudes. A hierarchical analysis using structural equation modeling showed that motivation-related variables are the main predictors of attitudes towards mathematics and that teachers and the social support of colleagues are also highly significant in understanding these attitudes.

Das, B (1988) studied secondary school teachers' job satisfaction and job motivation in Cuttack district of Orissa. Her objectives was to study the extent of job satisfaction in and motivation of : *i*) rural and urban teachers, *ii*) trained and untrained teachers, *iii*) male and female teachers, *iv*) government school and private school teachers and *v*) teachers from different age groups. Her findings were – Teachers who were motivated were also found highly satisfied in their jobs, 92% rural and 24% urban teachers, 62% trained and 46% untrained teachers, 53% male and female teachers, 77% government and 25% private school teachers are satisfied with their jobs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To compare social motives between male and female secondary school teachers.
2. To compare social motives between rural and urban secondary school teachers.
3. To compare social motives between trained and untrained secondary school teachers.

HYPOTHESES

H_0 : There would be no significant difference between male secondary school teachers and female secondary school teachers in their social motives.

H_0^2 : There would be no significant difference between rural secondary school teachers and urban secondary school teachers in their social motives.

H_0^3 : There would be no significant difference between trained secondary school teachers and untrained secondary school teachers in their social motives.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The quantitative approach was used by the present researcher as it was the most appropriate design for this research. The investigation was reductionist in nature. The study employed a survey

design also in which surveys were conducted by the present researcher personally to collect all the data from the respondent teachers.

Variables

Major variables – Social motives

Categorical variables – Gender (Male-Female), Locale (Rural-Urban) and Training (Trained-Untrained)

POPULATION & SAMPLE

The population of the study was all secondary school teachers of West Bengal, teaching in the secondary schools under control of West Bengal Board of Secondary Education (WBBSE). Out of 23 districts of West Bengal, 13 districts were selected randomly and from those 13 districts 72 secondary schools were selected randomly and from those 72 secondary schools, 7 teachers were selected randomly from each of the school.

TOOLS

In measuring Social Motives of the secondary school teachers, the standardized scale, Social Motive Scale (SMS), by Dr. Singh and Dr. Pandey (2010) was adapted and used. In this scale five consecutive alternatives were given in its twenty statements. The respondent had to tick (✓) any one alternative among five alternatives.

SCORING PROCEDURE

For the scale, Likert continuum - strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree had been provided to each item. Each item alternative was assigned a weight ranging from 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree) for favorable items and in the case of unfavorable items the range of weight was reversed *i.e.* from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree).

PRESENTATION OF DATA

The presentation of data, collected by the present researcher was done in order to make inferences and generalizations about the population. After that data were tabulated and descriptive statistics were computed. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 22.0 was used for this purpose. In the following segment these are depicted briefly.

Table-1: Descriptive Statistics for Social Motives

Social Motives		N Statistic	Mean		Median Statistic	SD Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
			Std. Error	Statistic			Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
Total		382	77.209	.3207	77.000	6.2681	.311	.125	-.233	.249
Gender	Male	174	78.253	.4909	78.000	6.4758	.165	.184	-.106	.366
	Female	208	76.337	.4136	76.000	5.6955	.411	.169	-.300	.336
Locale	Rural	211	77.303	.4560	77.000	6.6234	.302	.167	-.147	.333
	Urban	171	77.094	.4448	77.000	5.8171	.302	.186	-.527	.369

Social Motives		N Statistic	Mean		Median Statistic	SD Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
			Std. Error	Statistic			Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
Training	Trained	282	76.848	.3750	76.000	6.2976	.363	.145	-.178	.289
	Untrained	100	78.230	.6100	78.000	6.0999	.107	.241	-.157	.478

The above table shows that, the total (N = 382) mean score in Social Motives is 77.209, Median is 77.000, SD is 6.2681, Skewness is .311 and Kurtosis is -.233. The corresponding scores of these regarding the categorical variables namely gender, locale and training are also presented in that table.

RESULTS

For the purpose, the raw data were tabulated in MS Excel 2007 and analyses of data were done by the statistical software, IBM SPSS 22.0.

Table-2: Group Statistics for Social Motives

		Variations	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Social Motives	Gender	Male	174	78.253	6.4758	.4909
		Female	208	76.337	5.9655	.4136
	Locale	Rural	211	77.303	6.6234	.4560
		Urban	171	77.094	5.8171	.4448
	Training	Trained	282	76.848	6.2976	.3750
		Untrained	100	78.230	6.0999	.6100

Table-3: Independent Samples Test for Social Motives

Social Motives	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Gender (Male vs. Female)	Equal Variances Assumed	.408	.523	3.007*	380	.003
Locale (Rural vs. Urban)	Equal Variances Assumed	.903	.343	.325#	380	.745
Training (Trained vs. Untrained)	Equal Variances Assumed	.212	.645	-1.902#	380	.058

* Not significant at the 0.05 level # Significant at the 0.05 level

To test the homogeneity of variance, Levene's Test for Equality of Variance was considered. It showed that the F value of male and female was .408, rural and urban was .903 and trained and untrained was .212 and p value of those were .523, .343 and .645 respectively which were higher than 0.05, so the equal variances were assumed in the data. The table showed that t values were 3.007, .325 and 1.902 respectively, calculated for male & female, rural & urban and trained

& untrained school teachers with df 380 and p values were .003 ($p < 0.05$), .745 ($p > 0.05$) and .058 ($p > 0.05$) respectively, hence the H_{02} and H_{03} were not rejected but H_{01} was rejected. Then it can be said that, there was no significant differences between rural & urban teachers and trained & untrained teachers. But there was significant difference between male & female teachers in their social motives.

DISCUSSION

The result showed no significant difference between trained and untrained teachers and also between rural and urban school teachers in the present research but significant difference was there between male and female school teachers. The implication of it can be said that both the male and female teachers were differed in many situations like; trying to establish participation with others and making friendship with others, accepting responsibility for one's success or failure, always interested to know from others as to how he/she has done, are attempting to excel someone and trying to show something unusual and training making efforts to reach for distant goals, thinking about making further advancement, fixing high standards for oneself and while facing difficulties to be interested in making one's best effort. On the other hand, both the rural & urban school teachers and trained & untrained school teachers were of same opinions like; they are trying to be liked by others and indicating behavior like visiting to meet others, making arrangements for breakfast and food, attending clubs, accepting membership of institutions and parties etc, making effort to gain position and prestige and try to influence other person or group and they have strong desires for competing others, engaging one in such activities which generates conflicts, tensions or intense feeling, *for example*, to fall in discussion, to demand, to tell, to command, to punish others, controlling the flow of information and have the eagerness to know about one's influence on others, trying to get social appreciation to reach for distant goals, thinking about making further advancement, fixing high standards for oneself and while facing difficulties to be interested in making one's best effort.

CONCLUSION

The education system and especially teachers have very important roles in raising a healthy society and qualified individuals. The teacher has the power to influence all other variables about education. In order to be successful in teaching profession, one needs to love the profession and perform it willingly. The Secondary Education Commission (1952-1953) report rightly stated, "We are convinced that the most important factor in the contemplated educational reconstruction is the teacher, his personal qualities, his educational qualifications, his professional training and the place that he occupies in the community". The National Policy of Education (1986) also stated is this respecting that, "It is very right that, no people can rise above the level of its teachers." Studies related to explanation of human behavior have revealed that behavior is purposive, *i.e.*, determined by the anticipation of results. Human responses are not only simply controlled by stimulus situation but he consciously controls his dynamic mechanism to reach his goals. A healthy and useful communication process should be established between the teachers and the society. The profession should be improved in terms of theoretical, social and cultural aspects for an increased interest in the profession and more positive attitudes. In sum, this piece of research could have an impact on the field of educational research in India and subsequently may be a step towards the enrichment of knowledge of social motivation of teachers, not only for India but also for other developing countries.

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